

Numerical Modelling of the Spatial Distribution and Properties of Sub-seismic Faulting in Regions Containing Major Faults

SPRING3D - DENSITY

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
2. PROJECT OBJECTIVES	6
3. THE SPRING3D MODEL.....	6
3.1. Model description	6
3.2. Strain parameters from the mesh co-ordinates.....	8
3.3. Poisson's ratio in the Spring3D model	8
4. Model results.....	9
4.1. Example 1: Single vertical fault.....	10
4.2. Example 2: Faults in the Base Brent from a reservoir in the North Sea.	13
4.2.1. Setting up model runs	14
4.1.1. Estimating minor fault density	15
4.2.3. Estimating minor fault strike direction	16
4.2.4. Comparing model results to observed minor faulting.....	16
6. Discussion	19
6.3. A comparison between Spring3D and Poly3D	19
6.3. Future developments	19
7. References	21
8. Appendix A. Calculating strain parameters from the deformed mesh.....	22
9. Appendix B: Determining Poisson's ratio for the spring mesh model Spring3D.....	24
10. Appendix C: Procedure for running models with spring3d	26
11. Appendix D: The relationship between stress and strain, and measures of fault density	28

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A spring mesh model, Spring3D, that simulates the spatial distribution of strain around major faults is presented. The model is based on the physics of purely elastic media and is composed of a regular 2D mesh of springs. The position of the model's external boundaries and displacement on faults form the boundary conditions which are determined from an elevation map of the horizon to be modelled. Two examples are run: 1) a vertical fault with an elliptical displacement profile and 2) a series of faults in the Base Brent horizon in the vicinity of a reservoir in the North Sea. In both these cases, the Spring3D results are compared with those from a full 3D model, Poly3D, that has been used with success to predict sub-seismic scale faulting in a number of reservoirs around the world.

A comparison of the results shows that, although not identical, Spring3D and Poly3D model results show the same major characteristics. In the case of the single vertical fault, it is seen that Spring3D spreads deformation further out into the elastic medium than Poly3D. In the case of the faulted reservoir example, Spring3D and Poly3D predict broadly similar faulting density and fault strike. This is in agreement with the observed faulting (from seismically resolved small faults) over more than 60% of the modelled region.

The principal advantage of the Spring3D model is that much less information is required to run the model. Full 3D information on the position and displacement on faults is only available after 3D seismic surveys have been run and much data analysis has been done. During the exploration phase, it is much more common to have only information on the geometry of a few key horizons. Thus, although the Spring3D model does not treat the rock mass as rigorously as the Poly3D model, it could potentially be used to estimate the spatial distribution of sub-seismic scale fracturing and faulting in terms of type and intensity at the exploration stage. This additional information could then be used to help build models of the spatial distribution of permeability for flow simulations, especially early in the life of a field.

The Spring3D model is still in the early stages of development and a number of features would benefit from further development. These include particularly the discretization scheme for creating input files, inclusion for different types of boundary conditions, investigations into the role of spring constants in determining the geometry of the layer, model output in terms of stress as well as strain and calibration with field examples.

1. BACKGROUND

Displacement on large faults creates permanent deformation in the rock volume adjacent to the faults which is expressed as fracturing, minor faulting, and folding. The location and nature of folding can be evaluated through horizon maps constructed from seismic sections. However, a significant amount of faulting and fracturing lies below seismic resolution and there exists no direct method for their detection. It is known from field studies that the spatial distribution and geometry of sub-seismic fracturing and minor faulting associated with major faults varies in response to (e.g.) fault shape, proximity to other faults and layer mechanical properties, often in a manner which is not easy to predict intuitively (e.g. Jamieson and Stearns 1982). These variations will influence the fluid flow characteristics of the rocks including hydraulic properties of faults and their damage zones, degree to which a reservoir may be 'compartmentalized' with respect to hydrocarbon occurrence and fluid pressures, and effectiveness of cap rocks. A model which can predict the nature and spatial distribution of brittle deformation in the vicinity of major faults would provide a valuable tool in the evaluation of reservoir and cap rock quality, and effective fracture permeability.

In recent years, numerical modelling has played an increasingly important role in the prediction of reservoir behaviour. These models have largely concentrated on predicting lithological heterogeneities (sedimentary architecture) and fluid flow during production (oil, gas and water). Until very recently, models of the spatial variability and intensity of small scale faulting and fracturing in regions of major faults have been very rudimentary and based on simple stochastic and conceptual modelling of fracture systems. Such models fail to account for the manner in which major faults interact and how this affects the deformation of the rock mass.

Models of deformation around faults based on elastic theory have been successfully applied in the past and shown to give good agreement with observations (e.g. Massonet et al. 1993). In recent work at Norsk Hydro's Research Centre in Bergen, a three dimensional model, called Poly3D, has been used to compute stresses and strains in rock volumes around major faults. This research has been conducted by Paul Gillespie of Norsk Hydro AS and members of the Rock Deformation Project at Stanford University, led by Prof. Dave Pollard. This research has shown how effectively models based on the principals of elastic media can simulate the stress and strain state of deformed rock masses. Poly3D has been used successfully to predict sub-seismic faulting type and intensity in a number of hydrocarbon reservoirs around the world (e.g. Gillespie 1999, Maerten et al submitted). This type of modelling represent a significant advance in the prediction of the spatial distribution of sub-seismic faulting both with respect to fault type and fault density.

The Poly3D model requires three dimensional information on the geometry of faults and their displacement fields. This requires a detailed 3D seismic survey of the modelled region which may not always be available, especially during the exploration phase of potential fields. At NERSC there exists a model, called Spring3D, which uses the geometry of a single given horizon displaced by major faults (as oppose to the geometry of the whole 3D rock volume) to compute the strains in the plane of the horizon. This model is based on a mesh of elastic ‘springs’ which simulate the behaviour of a single horizon. Both Spring3D and Poly3d are based on the physics of a purely elastic medium but they use different numerical modelling approaches.

The strain field determined by Spring3D can provide a guide to the nature and intensity of sub-seismic faulting. Since this model simulates only a single layer within the rock mass, it requires only information about the fault locations and displacement in this layer. Maps of specific horizons are often produced during exploration so that this information is normally available at a much earlier stage in the life of a field. Requiring less detailed information means that the Spring3D model is also potentially quicker to set up and run. Thus, while Spring3D does not treat the rock volume as rigorously as Poly3D, potentially it could provide a guide to the strain field and prediction of sub-seismic faulting at an early stage in the life of a field, that could be followed up at a later stage by more rigorous and complete modelling using Poly3D. The Spring3D model is still in the early stages of development and the main purpose of this pilot project is to run two cases and to compare the results with those of Poly3D to assess the applicability of the simpler mesh model.

2.PROJECT OBJECTIVES

- 1) To use a numerical model, Spring3D, that simulates strain in layers around major faults to predict the spatial distribution of sub-seismic faulting intensity and orientation.
- 2) To use the results from the numerical model to quantitatively analyse the spatial relationship between seismically resolvable faults and sub-seismic faulting.

3.THE SPRING3D MODEL

3.1. MODEL DESCRIPTION

The model Spring3D predicts the strain in a rock layer from the location and displacement on major (seismically resolved) faults and the geometry of a horizon.

The input required for the model is a elevation map of a faulted horizon. Output from the model is a series of maps showing the spatial distribution of strain parameters in the layer.

The model is based on a numerical mesh of 'springs' which obey Hooke's law:

$$F = -k\Delta l \quad (1)$$

where F is the force resulting in a change of spring length, Δl , and k is the 'spring' constant. A corresponding equation exists for the bending of springs. This equation is directly equivalent to the equation relating stress to change in length for an elastic medium (Ramsay 1967):

$$\sigma = -Ee \quad (2)$$

where σ is stress, E is Young's modulus and e is the change in length in the direction in which the stress, σ , is applied.

Fig.1 The geometry of the spring mesh in Spring3d. The diagonals are required to make the mesh resist shear.

The Spring3D model is based on a mesh of springs forming a square grid with diagonals, see Fig.1. The diagonals are required so that the mesh resists shear deformation. Each spring is assigned elastic constants which determine how the spring's length changes and how the spring bends with applied stress. The resistance of the mesh to bending (given by the bending spring constants) simulates the effects of the geological layers above and below.

The location and displacements of known faults are introduced into the model. The numerical mesh is 'cut' along the line of each fault and opposite sides of these cuts are displaced and fixed at positions corresponding to the known displacements on the faults (see Fig.3 for an example). These displacements create stresses in the mesh as the springs deform to accommodate displacements on the faults.

The equilibrium configuration of the spring mesh corresponds to that in which the total summed energy stored in the springs is a minimum, where energy T for a single spring is given by:

$$T = k\Delta l^2 \quad (3)$$

This configuration is determined by the numerical model. The model makes an initial estimate of the mesh geometry by solving the corresponding pressure equation for the x, y and z co-ordinates independently. This provides a fairly good initial guess at the equilibrium configuration of the mesh so that the final solution, which is solved by slower 'sequential under relaxation' (SUR) methods, is reached faster. The equilibrium geometry of the mesh depends on the strength of the springs given by the elastic constants (stretching/compression and bending) and the boundary conditions consisting of the position of nodes lying on the fault planes and on the external boundaries of the modelled area.

3.2. STRAIN PARAMETERS FROM THE MESH CO-ORDINATES

When the lowest energy configuration of the mesh has been found, the deformations suffered by each spring (stretching-compression, bending) in accommodating the displacements on the faults are used to create maps of strain parameters. These maps provide a guide to the spatial variation in fracturing/faulting intensity and the orientation and displacement sense on minor faults. In the grid, each mesh cell outlined by four grid nodes defines a square which becomes a trapezoid after the displacements on faults and external boundaries are modelled. From the shape and size of each trapezoid, the parameters of the strain ellipse in the plane of the modelled layer can be calculated. These comprise the length of the major axes, a and b , and their orientations. The method of calculating these parameters from the mesh co-ordinates is outlined in Appendix A.

3.3. POISSON'S RATIO IN THE SPRING3D MODEL

As part of the model input, the Poly3D model uses Young's modulus, E , and Poisson's ratio, ν , representative for the rock mass modelled. It has been shown above that the spring constants used by Spring3D are equivalent to Young's modulus (equations 1 and 2). However, the spring mesh model does not use any other elastic constant directly. Poisson's ratio is the ratio of elongation to compression suffered by a bar which is stretched parallel to its length but otherwise unconstrained (Ramsay 1967). In order to find out the value of Poisson's ratio for the spring mesh, a single cell composed of springs in the X and Y direction with two diagonals is considered, see Fig2a. An elongation of the Y springs, Δl_1 , is imposed and the forces in the X and diagonal springs balanced to determine the compression, Δl_2 , in the X direction. Poisson's ratio is then this compression

divided by the imposed elongation. The details of these arguments are given in Appendix B. Poisson's ratio for the mesh model was found to decrease with increasing elongation imposed on the cell and ranges from 0.33 to 0.25 with elongation from 0 to 1, see Fig.2b. However, during the runs for the two fault examples it was found that over 95% of the cells have suffered elongations less than 0.2, so that the effective Poisson's ratio for the model is 0.33. This compares with 0.25 (vertical fault example) and 0.15 (fault system example) used in Poly3D runs.

Fig.2 A: Poisson's ratio for the model mesh is calculated by considering one spring mesh cell with diagonals. B: Plot of Poisson's ratio versus elongation for the spring mesh model, Spring3D.

4. MODEL RESULTS

In this pilot project, the Spring 3D model is to be used to create maps of strain parameters for two examples. These are (1) a single vertical fault and (2) an area of major faulting in the Base Brent horizon from a North Sea hydrocarbon reservoir. The Spring 3D model results will be compared to the same examples simulated by Poly3D, to compare the two modelling approaches. The resulting maps will also be compared to the observed fault map of the modelled area in example 2 to assess the potential of the model as a predictive tool for sub-seismic faulting.

4.1. EXAMPLE 1: SINGLE VERTICAL FAULT

A simple model of a single vertical fault was run with Spring3d and Poly3D for comparison purposes. A vertical fault parallel to the X axis was placed in the centre of a square region, see Fig.3. The fault was given a length one half of the modelled region width. A total displacement (throw) of 4.0 units was imposed at the centre of the fault. The model was run using poly3D with an observation plane of points through the pre-displacement centre of the fault. This plane contained a initially square grid of points which recorded the strains in this plane after deformation. Poly3D then generated the displacement profile on the fault and determined the stress and strain fields in the surrounding rock volume. When running Spring3D, it was found that the initial estimate gave very low total energies and further adjustments of the spring mesh were small. The model was run for a total of 500 iterations which took about 20 minutes on an IBM Risc 6000 workstation. Increasing the number of iterations to 1000 was not found to significantly alter the results.

Fig.3 The configuration of the mesh for the vertical fault example. The mesh has a dimension of 200 by 200. For simplicity, only every 10th grid line is shown here. The vertical fault has a vertical displacement of 4 mesh units.

For Spring3D, an elliptical displacement profile for the fault with a maximum displacement of 4.0 units was used as input to the model. This closely approximates to the displacement profile of the fault determined by Poly3D. The boundaries of the square region containing the fault were fixed at their original locations. The model was run with a mesh of 200 by 200 nodes. The geometry and

strain parameters of the spring mesh layer (Spring3D) and grid of observation points (Poly3D) were calculated and are compared in Figures 3 and 4.

Comparing the results of Spring3d with Poly3D shows that they give broadly similar results with some small differences. Poly3D tends to let displacement ‘leak’ out into the unfaulted medium at the fault tips. This means that the fault in poly3D is a little longer than it should be. The post-displacement geometry of the plane, the strain intensity and the direction of the minimum strain axis (direction of compression) for the results from Poly3D and spring3D are plotted in Fig.4.

Fig.4a Vertical fault results – height. Spring3D transmits deformation further into the model away from the fault than Poly3D.

The plots showing the layer geometry (Fig.4a) show that Spring3D propagates displacement of the layer further into the modelled region from the fault plane than Poly3D. This is also reflected by the plots of strain intensity (defined as $(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})$ where a and b are the maximum and minimum strain ellipse axes) which show that Poly3D concentrates deformation closer to the fault plane than Spring3D. The plots of maximum compressive strain axis orientation for Poly3D and Spring3D (Fig.4c) are, however, very similar with the only noticeable differences occurring along extensions

Fig4b. Vertical fault results – strain intensity. Strain intensity is defined as $(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})$. The Poly3D model concentrates deformation closer to the fault plane than Spring3D.

Fig4c. Vertical fault results – direction minimum strain axis, *b*. The two models, Spring3D and Poly3D, show very similar results.

of the fault itself. Although strains are very high in the immediate vicinity of the fault tip, as is shown by the plots of strain intensity, strains along this line away from the fault tip are very low indeed (<0.0001). Here the strain ellipse is so close to a circle that the directions of the major axes are easily interchanged. Fig.5 shows the difference in the height of the layer between the results for Spring3D and Poly3d. The maximum difference occurs a little distance from the fault mid-point on either side of the fault. The maximum difference is around one half of a model cell which is 0.25% of the model size. The differences between Spring 3D and Poly3D model results are therefore minimal.

Fig5. The difference in height between model results for Spring3D and PolyD for the vertical fault example. The maximum difference is less than one half of one cell (0.25% of the model size).

4.2. EXAMPLE 2: FAULTS IN THE BASE BRENT FROM A RESERVOIR IN THE NORTH SEA.

This example contains four major faults which displace the Base Brent horizon in an area in the North Sea. A map of the faults derived from a 3D seismic survey is shown in Fig.6. This shows major and minor faults with a variety of orientations. The four largest faults, shown in grey in Fig.6, were chosen to as input to the model. The remaining faults were then used as a guide to small scale faulting against which the model results were tested. This example has already been simulated using Poly3D (Gillespie 1999, Maerten et al., submitted) where the full 3D geometry of the faults was included.

4.2.1. Setting up model runs

In the Poly3D study, it has been determined from palinspastic reconstructions that the whole area has undergone a general strain in the X, Y and Z directions, $e_x=0.13$, $e_y=0.04$, $e_z=-0.17$ (Gillespie 1999, Maerten et al., submitted). These strains have been included in both the Poly3D and Spring3D models.

Fig.7 show a map of the Base Brent horizon in the modelled area. This map has been used to construct input files for Spring3D. The traces of the four major faults within this horizon form internal boundary conditions while the elevation of the Base Brent at the map boundaries give the outer boundary conditions. The procedures used to create the input files for Spring3D are outlined in Appendix C.

Fig.6 Map of faults in the Base Brent horizon with the modelled region outlined. The faults modelled are shown in grey while the remaining faults are used to test model results. (After Maerten et al., Submitted)

The results from Poly3D and Spring3D are shown in Figs.7, 8 and 9. The map of the layer elevation resulting from the Spring3D model is shown in Fig.7b. The Spring3D model has been forced to agreement with the map along the faults and at the map edge which form the boundary conditions to the model. Elsewhere, the observed map shows effects of minor faulting, but the modelled and observed maps show overall good agreement.

MAP BASE BRENT

Fig.7 Left – observed map of the Base Brent in the modelled area, Right – modelled geometry of the horizon output from Spring3D. F1 to F4 are the major modelled faults. Heights are in metres relative to a depth of 3000m.

4.1.1. Estimating minor fault density

In Poly3D modelling, the maximum Coulomb shear stress, S_c , was used as a measure of the faulting density (Gillespie 1999, Maerten et al., submitted) where:

$$S_c = \frac{(\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)\sqrt{1 - \mu^2}}{2} - \frac{(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)\mu}{2} \quad (4)$$

This formulation uses the maximum and minimum 3D stresses, σ_1 and σ_3 , together with the coefficient of friction, μ . Although Spring3D calculates stresses in the mesh, the output is at present in the form of strains only. In addition, Spring3D can only give the strains in the plane of the modelled layer whereas equation (3) uses the 3D stress system. However, using the relationship between stress and strain for elastic solids (Ramsay 1967) and employing the simple assumption that the maximum compressive stress is vertical and due to overburden, an equivalent expression can be determined in terms of strain in the plane of the modelled layer. The derivation of the final expression (equation 5) is given in Appendix D. Using the values of Young's Modulus, $E=65000$, Poisson's ration, $\nu=0.15$ and the coefficient of friction $\mu=0.65$ used in the Poly3D model then gives the following formula:

$$S_c = 100000(6.0a + 0.7b - 5.7) \quad (5)$$

where a and b are the maximum and minimum axes of the strain ellipse in the plane of the layer. For Spring3D model results, expression (5) is used as a measure of faulting density and compared to the results from Poly3D where expression (4) has been used, in Fig.8. The two figures show a generally similar pattern with very low intensities between faults 2 and 3 and in the southern part of the area between faults 3 and 4 and high intensities the area west of fault 1 and on the western side of fault 4. Spring3D results show a less pronounced zone of high intensities west of fault 4 and lower intensities on the extreme eastern margin of the model, and higher intensities in the small area between faults 1 and 2 compared to Poly3D. However, some of the details of the intensity fields of both models also show good correspondence. There are high intensity areas on the outside of bends in the faults, especially for fault 2 and 4, and low intensity areas on the inside of bends, especially for fault 4.

4.2.3. Estimating minor fault strike direction

For the Poly3D model, the direction of the intermediate stress axis is used as an indicator of the strike of minor faulting. As a substitute for this, the direction of the minor strain axis (maximum compressive strain, b) in the plane of the layer was used in the Spring3D results. The results of both models are compared in Fig.9. Generally there is good agreement between the two direction fields. The dominant direction is N-S with variations through to E-W in especially the area between faults 2 and 3 and close to all faults. The biggest differences between the model results are in the southernmost part of the area between faults 2 and 3 and faults 3 and 4 where Spring3D predicts more westerly trends than Poly3D.

4.2.4. Comparing model results to observed minor faulting

The results of the two models (Poly3D and Spring3D) are also compared to the minor faulting. The density estimated from occurrence of seismically resolvable minor faulting (Marten et al. Submitted) is shown in Fig.8 (top) and compared to the predictions by Spring3D and Poly3D, Fig.8 (bottom). Generally Poly3D seems to predict smoother variations in the density field than Spring3D. In this respect, the Spring3D results show a better resemblance to nature. Spring3D model results show the same areas of high density in the area between faults 3 and 4 adjacent to bends in fault 4, whereas Poly3D has predicted a general N-S trending zone with constantly high density. Spring3D also predicts higher densities west of faults 1 and 2, more in agreement with the observed pattern. Poly3D seems to be in better agreement with the observed density field to the

east of fault 4, where Spring3D densities are low, and between faults 1 and 2 where Spring3D densities are high.

In Fig.9, the direction of minor fault strike is predicted by the minimum strain axis, b , in Spring3D, and by the intermediate stress direction by Poly3D. In this case the Spring3D and Poly3D predictions are very similar over most of the model. The greatest differences occur between faults 1 and 2, and between faults 3 and 4. Between faults 1 and 2, Spring3D has not managed to predict the N-S trending strikes in the southern part of this area where Poly3D has been more successful. In the area between faults 3 and 4, Spring3D predicts more varying strikes than Poly3D. In this area, the

SPRING3D - DENSITY

Fig.8 Top: Fault density from observed minor faults. Bottom left: fault density from Spring3D model, bottom right: fault density from Poly3D model. Top and bottom right from Maertens et al (submitted).

SPRING3D - DIRECTION

Fig.9 Top: observed strike of minor faulting. Bottom left – predicted direction of minor faulting from Spring3D and right predicted direction of minor faulting from Poly3D.

observed fault strike switches repeatedly between NE and NW strikes. The NE fault strikes are not predicted by Poly3D but better approximated by Spring3D. The NW strikes in the southern part of this area are not predicted by either model except for Spring3D in the extreme south of this region.

6. DISCUSSION

6.3. A COMPARISON BETWEEN SPRING3D AND POLY3D

Both Spring3D and Poly3D model work on the principals of deformation of a purely elastic medium. The numerical approaches to modelling are, however, different. Poly3D is a boundary element code where only the faults are discretised. It is a fully 3D model which requires the displacement fields on fault planes as input. Spring3D uses much simpler numerical method (SOR - sequential under relaxation) and models only a single layer in the rock volume. It requires the displacement of faults in this horizon only as input.

The two worked examples show that Spring3D gives results that are similar, although not identical, to those of Poly3D. The simple model of the vertical faults shows that Spring3D tends to dissipate deformation further into the elastic medium away from the fault than Poly3D. In the more complex example of faulting in a North Sea reservoir, the two models are in general agreement on the main features of the faulting intensity and strike direction of minor faulting. Generally, Spring3D tends to produce a more complex faulting intensity field than Poly3D but many of these features were in agreement with the observed faulting intensity.

The principal advantage of the Spring3D over the Poly3D model is that much less information is required to run the model. Full 3D information on the position and displacement on faults is only be available after 3D seismic surveys have been run and much data analysis has been done. At the exploration phase of a field it is much more common to have only information on the geometry of a few key horizons. Thus, although the Spring3D model does not treat the rock mass in as rigorous a fashion as the Poly3D model, it could potentially be used to estimate the spatial distribution of sub-seismic scale fracturing and faulting in terms of type and intensity. This additional information could be used to help build models of the spatial distribution of permeability for flow simulations, especially early in the life of a field.

6.3. FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

The Spring3D model is still in the early stages of development and the two worked examples are among the first examples to be run. It is promising therefore that the model gave results comparable with those of Poly3D.

There are a number of features of the Spring3D model that need further investigation and development:

- 1) Two spring constants (stretch/compression and bending) are used in the model. The bending constant gives the modelled layer resistance to sudden changes in orientation and to some extent simulates the effects of the rock mass above and below. The effects of varying the ratio between stretch/compression and bending spring constants has yet to be fully explored. At present the mesh has an effective Poisson's ratio of 0.33 which is quite high for rocks. Modifying the spring constants so that different values are used for stretch and compression may be a way of varying the effective Poisson's ratio in the mesh.
- 2) Since the model discretizes the entire layer it is possible (although not presently implemented in the model) to vary these spring constants over the modelled layer, in contrast to Poly3D which assumes the rock volume to be a homogenous medium. This possibility in Spring3D could be used to model relatively weak areas (where there is known to be intense open fracturing or where dissolution processes have reduced the cementation) and relatively strong area (areas of mineral precipitation or lithological variation such as sandstone-shale transitions). Varying the spring constants will change the shape of the modelled layer which could be calibrated against the observed horizon geometry.
- 2) The external boundary conditions in the present model are to fix the mesh nodes at the outer boundaries of the model to given (x, y, z) co-ordinates. More flexible boundary conditions could be included such as fixing two edges of the model or fixing only the Y co-ordinate. Other free-er boundary conditions could be imposed by embedding the modelled region in a outer more pliable mesh region. This would allow the external boundaries of the area of interest to take up more natural positions and reduce the influence of the outer boundary conditions on the model results.
- 3) At the time of this report, only mesh sizes of either 200 by 200 or 100 by 100 can be run. With small alterations to the code, any size of grid could be modelled. In addition, output in terms of stresses, as well as strains, should be implemented.
- 4) The area where most work is still required is in the discretization of faults and setting up of the boundary conditions. To create model input, the pre-displacement position of the fault traces in the plane of the modelled layer must be discretized and displaced to their present position. In the model results, it can be seen that there are many cells immediately adjacent to faults where very high strains are recorded. These are grid cells where two or more nodes are fixed (at the fault plane). Large strain are possible because the present discretization scheme does not ensure

that these cells maintain reasonable shapes. This sometimes causes problems when running the model so that some manual adjustment of nodes positions can be required. It would greatly speed up the process of setting up the model input files and running the model, if a better and more automated discretization scheme was developed.

- 5) The step from strain parameters to faulting type and intensity is still a subject of research. It would be highly informative to model a region where the minor faulting could be observed in outcrop. Here the meaning of the various stress and strain parameters determined by the model could be tested against observed type and density of faulting and fracturing.

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8. APPENDIX A. CALCULATING STRAIN PARAMETERS FROM THE DEFORMED MESH.

The output from model 'Spring3D' is a list of the (x,y,z) coordinates of the initially regular grid of nodes in the mesh. Four nodes which initially defined a square, now define an irregular trapezoid. The method of calculating the strain parameters for each cell in the mesh, in the plane of the layer is outlined below.

In the above figure, the square defined by point (x_1, y_1) is deformed to the trapezoid defined by point (x, y) . The strain is described by the strain ellipse with axes l_1 and l_2 at angles θ_1 and $\theta_2 = 90 + \theta_1$, to the X axis.

The equation for the strain ellipse is:

$$Ax^2 - 2Cxy + By^2 = 1$$

where

$$A = (c^2 + d^2) / (ad - bc)^2$$

$$B = (a^2 + b^2) / (ad - bc)^2$$

$$C = (ac + bd) / (ad - bc)^2$$

In matrix form this is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x & y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & C \\ C & B \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = 1$$

The lengths of the principal axes of the strain ellipse are give by the eigenvalues, and their directions by the eigenvectors of the matrix $\begin{bmatrix} A & C \\ C & B \end{bmatrix}$.

The eigenvalues are given by:

$$\lambda_1, \lambda_2 = \left((A+B) \pm \sqrt{(A+B)^2 - 4(AB-C^2)} \right) / 2$$

The lengths of the strain ellipse major axes are then given by:

$$l_1 = 1/\sqrt{\lambda_2} \quad \text{and} \quad l_2 = 1/\sqrt{\lambda_1}$$

The orientation of the prinicipal axes, θ_1 and θ_2 , are given by:

$$\theta_1 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\lambda_2 - A}{C} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \theta_2 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\lambda_1 - A}{C} \right)$$

9. APPENDIX B: DETERMINING POISSON'S RATIO FOR THE SPRING MESH MODEL SPRING3D

The effective Poisson's ratio for the spring mesh model, Spring3D, is determined by considering a single cell composed of 4 nodes connected by springs in the X and Y directions and along the diagonals of the cell.

Poisson's ratio, ν , is the ratio of elongation in the X and Y direction of a bar that is stretched in the Y direction but unconstrained in the X direction:

$$\nu = \frac{\Delta l_2}{\Delta l_1}$$

This is simulated by imposing elongations, Δl_1 , on the springs in the Y direction. The resulting elongation in the X direction, Δl_2 , is calculated by balancing the forces exerted by the springs along the diagonals of the cell and in the X direction.

The change in length of the diagonal springs is:

$$\Delta l_D = \sqrt{2} - (1 + \Delta l_1) / \sin \theta$$

And the force exerted by these springs in the X direction is:

$$F_{Dx} = -k(\sqrt{2} - (1 + \Delta l_1) / \sin \theta) \cos \theta$$

The force exerted by the springs parallel to X is:

$$F_x = -k\Delta l_2 \quad \text{where} \quad \Delta l_2 = ((1 + \Delta l_1) / \tan \theta) - 1$$

The forces must balance, so that:

$$(\sqrt{2} - (1 + \Delta l_1) / \sin \theta) \cos \theta = ((1 + \Delta l_1) / \tan \theta) - 1$$

Rearranging and gathering terms gives:

$$2(1 + \Delta l_1) = \tan \theta + \sqrt{2} \sin \theta$$

This equation can be solved iteratively for θ and thus for Δl_2 given Δl_1 .

10. APPENDIX C: PROCEDURE FOR RUNNING MODELS WITH SPRING3D

Creating boundary files for Spring3D

Two files containing the boundary nodes and their (x, y, z) co-ordinates are required:

a) File containing internal boundary nodes

This file contains a list of nodes on faults inside the outer boundaries of the model. Each fault is defined by two traces representing the intersection of the layer with the foot-wall and the hanging-wall of each fault. Program 'fdisct.f' is used to help create this file. The program takes the eastern-most fault trace (assumed to be the foot-wall) and discretized it onto the model grid (200x200). The program then creates another discretized trace one grid element to the left which does not overlap with the first. Then these two traces are mapped onto the input points defining the hanging and foot-wall traces of the fault from the map of the layer to be modelled.

This is done by finding the point on the mapped trace that is closest to each node and is designed for mapped traces that are digitized with many points with a spacing smaller than the size of a model grid cell. This is a simple method but has some disadvantages. It works well for the foot-wall because the distance between the discretized and map traces is not great. However for the hanging-wall trace, the distances are greater and it is possible to get several nodes mapped onto the same point. This can cause large jumps in the (x, y, z) co-ordinates along the fault trace which can cause problems in running the model. At present the only solution is to go into the file and manually correct such occurrences. During runs, the model lists the nodes for which there are the greatest force imbalances in the X, Y and Z direction after every 10th iteration. Run the model until the total energy starts to dramatically increase. Record the (x, y) node co-ordinates when this occurs and check these places in the internal boundary node file.

Program 'fdisct.f' does not deal in any special way with fault intersections and large jumps in x, y or z co-ordinates can occur at these places. The model cannot handle nodes in the grid that are surrounded by three known nodes, i.e. enclaves in the fault traces. Program fdisct.f removes these from each trace it creates but does not check for this occurrence at fault intersections. It is necessary at present, to go in to the files and manually adjust nodes around intersection to make smooth variation in (x, y, z) co-ordinates and eliminate enclaves in traces. Removing enclaves can be done by adding the nodes in such enclaves to the list giving them (x, y, z) co-ordinates representative of their surroundings. It is advisable to add the faults to the model one at a time, making the necessary corrections as indicated by the model output. In this way the full model is built up piece-wise.

b) File containing external boundary nodes

Program fdisct.f also creates a file that list the outer boundary nodes for the model and their (x, y, z) co-ordinates. These are created from the input map, by finding the corresponding location in the map for each outer node. Where faults meet the outer boundaries, the program calculates a smooth transition in (x, y, z) co-ordinates across the fault, thus avoiding sudden jumps.

At present, the model must be run for mesh sizes of either 200 by 200, or 100 by 100. Other models can be run by extending the mesh to one of these sizes. This is done by program 'bounadj.f' which extends the mesh and the boundary conditions in the positive X and Y directions.

Both 'fdisct.f' and 'bounadj.f' are coded specifically for example 2 in this report (faults in the Base Brent in a reservoir in the North Sea). However, these programs can provide a starting point for programs to help create input files for other examples or towards more generally applicable programs to discretize the fault pattern.

Including global strains in X, Y and Z directions

The model generally only contains the largest faults and the limitation of map resolution means that many small faults are unknown. Thus the layer has suffered additional strain from the accumulated displacements on these small faults. To compensate for this, user defined global strains in X, Y and Z directions can be inserted into the model. To do this the locations of fault-layer intersection traces and the map of layer geometry are first 'unstrained' by applying the inverse of the user defined strains in the X, Y and Z directions. The fault traces are discretized and mapped onto the pre-strain layer map. These pre-strained locations are then mapped onto the post-strain locations represented by the fault traces and layer geometry in the present day state (original files). This is done in program 'fdisct'.

Other input to the model

Other user defined input to the model includes:

Number of iterations: It is best to run the model with 0 iterations first to check the first estimate for the layer geometry first, then to run the model for a number of iterations where the forces are iteratively balanced. Normally after 500 iterations there is very little change in the model. This can be monitored by comparing the total energy output by the model after every 10th iteration.

Iterative 'factor': The model approaches a state of equilibrium by calculating the distance a node must move in the X, Y and Z directions to balance the forces in its immediate surroundings. The program does this for each node independently. Because these distances are calculated using local conditions only, moving each node by these distances can cause 'overshoot' resulting in sudden large increases in total energy. This is avoided by moving each node by only a proportion of the calculated distances (SUR - sequential under relaxation). The proportion used is determined by the iterative 'factor' and is input interactively by the user at each run. Normally a factor of 5.0 works well (i.e. each node is moved a fifth of the calculated distance). If a layer geometry with very steep gradients is modelled, it may be that this factor needs to be increased.

Spring constants, kstr (stretch/compress) and kbd (bending): These are set in the program to 1.0 and 10.0 respectively. Increasing *kbd* does not seem to change the results significantly but reducing *kbd* to zero can. The precise meaning and effect of varying these quantities has not, at the time of this report, been fully explored. In the runs in this report these spring constants have been kept constant over the whole model. Since the whole layer is discretized, there exists the possibility of varying them over the model to simulate, for example, areas of weak rock where extensive open fractures are known to exist, or areas of strong rock where cementation is known to be extensive.

11. APPENDIX D: THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STRESS AND STRAIN, AND MEASURES OF FAULT DENSITY

The relationship between stress and strain for an elastic solid is given in Ramsay (1967), page 283:

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} [e_1(1-\nu) + \nu(e_2 + e_3)] \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_2 = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} [e_2(1-\nu) + \nu(e_1 + e_3)] \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_3 = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} [e_3(1-\nu) + \nu(e_1 + e_2)] \quad (3)$$

Where $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$ are the principal stresses, e_1, e_2, e_3 are the principal strains, E is Young's modulus and ν is Poisson's ratio.

In Poly3d modelling (Gillespie 1999, Maerten et al., submitted), the maximum shear Coulomb stress, S_c , is used to predict fault density, where:

$$S_c = \frac{(\sigma_3 - \sigma_1)\sqrt{1-\mu^2}}{2} - \frac{(\sigma_1 + \sigma_3)\mu}{2} \quad (4)$$

In all of the above equations, σ_1 is the maximum compressive stress. In Poly3D it was then assumed that σ_1 is everywhere near vertical and the direction of σ_2 was used to estimate fault strike.

Combining and rearranging the equations 1 and 3, we obtain the expressions:

$$(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3) = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)} [e_1 - e_3] \quad (5)$$

$$(\sigma_1 + \sigma_3) = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} [e_1 + e_3 + 2\nu e_2] \quad (6)$$

Substituting equations 5 and 6 into equation 4 gives:

$$S_c = C_1 e_1 + C_2 e_2 + C_3 e_3 \quad (7)$$

where C_1, C_2, C_3 are constants given by:

$$C_1 = \frac{(\sqrt{1+\mu^2}(1-2\nu) - \mu)E}{2(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \quad (8)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{\mu\nu E}{2(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \quad (9)$$

$$C_3 = \frac{(\sqrt{1+\mu^2(1-2\nu)} + \mu)E}{2(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)} \quad (10)$$

In the output of the model Spring3d, we calculate the 2D strain parameters in the plane of the layer (see Appendix A). These are close to e_2 and e_3 , while e_1 , the strain due to vertical stress is unknown. Stress in the vertical direction is due to overburden and can be assumed to be close to constant over the model. The average thickness of sediments at the depth of the layer modelled by Spring3D is 3000m. Assuming an average density of these sediments of 2200 kg/m^3 :

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_{gz} = 2200 \times 10 \times 3000 = 66000 \text{ MPa}$$

In addition, rearranging equation 1 gives:

$$e_1 = \frac{\sigma_1(1+\nu)(1-2\nu)}{E(1-\nu)} - \frac{\nu(e_2 + e_3)}{(1-\nu)} \quad (11)$$

so that equation 11 can be used to substitute for e_1 in equation 7.

Now in the Poly3d model, the parameters of the elastic medium were given values representative for loose sand. These are:

Young's modulus, $E = 65000$

Poisson's ratio, $\nu = 0.15$

Coefficient of friction, $\mu = 0.6$

Substituting these values into equation 7 and using equation 11, gives:

$$S_c = 10393 - 7387e_2 - 58718e_3$$

as the equivalent expression that can be evaluated for the output of the model Spring3d. This can be simplified to:

$$S_c = 10000(1 - 0.7e_2 - 6.0e_3)$$

Using the strain parameters the maximum and minimum strain ellipse axes, a and b , where $a = 1 + e_3$ and $b = 1 + e_2$ gives:

$$S_c = 10000(5.7 - 6.0a - 0.7b) \quad (12)$$

Equation 12 gives an approximation that can be used in Spring3D as an approximate equivalent to the maximum Coulomb shear stress (equation 4) and used to estimate the fault density predicted by the model.

